

The number of downloads for the bayesvl program increased significantly in January 2024

AISDL Team

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In the first month of 2024, there was a significant increase in the number of downloads for the Bayesian stats / MCMC computing program, *bayesvl*, developed by AISDL running on R and Stan. The following RDocumentation (CRAN) graph illustrates the noticeable leap in data for January 2024.

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bayesvl (version 0.8.5)

Visually Learning the Graphical Structure of Bayesian Networks and Performing MCMC with 'Stan'

Description

Provides users with its associated functions for pedagogical purposes in visually learning Bayesian networks and Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) computations. It enables users to: a) Create and examine the (starting) graphical structure of Bayesian networks; b) Create random Bayesian networks using a dataset with customized constraints; c) Generate 'Stan' code for structures of Bayesian networks for sampling the data and learning parameters; d) Plot the network graphs; e) Perform Markov chain Monte Carlo computations and produce graphs for posteriors checks. The package refers to one reference item, which describes the methods and algorithms: Vuong, Quan-Hoang and La, Viet-Phuong (2019) The 'bayesvl' R package. Open Science Framework (May 18).

MONTHLY DOWNLOADS

431

VERSION	LICENSE
0.8.5	GPL (>= 3)
ISSUES	PULL REQUESTS
1	0
STARS	FORKS
20	3

REPOSITORY <https://github.com/sshpa/bayesvl>

Illustration: The download history over the 12 months for the *bayesvl* program. (Accessed on February 1, 2024; <https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/bayesvl/versions/0.8.5>)

Specifically, with 431 downloads in January 2024, the *bayesvl* program shows a remarkable increase of +164% compared to December 2023. The number of downloads in January 2024 is also +96% higher than the monthly average in 2023.

One plausible explanation could be the growing interest in utilizing the BMF Analytics method, with many taking advantage of the year-end holidays to experiment with it. However, this is just a subjective speculation. Could it be that the mindsponge theory has garnered more attention?!

Nevertheless, with the positive surge in January, the total downloads of *bayesvl* from July 2021 to January 2024 have reached a cumulative total of 9568. The AISDL research team can now foresee reaching the 10K milestone in the not-too-distant future.

References

[1] La VP, Vuong QH. (2019). *bayesvl*: Visually learning the graphical structure of Bayesian networks and performing MCMC with 'Stan'. <https://cran.r-project.org/package=bayesvl>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (Eds.). (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH.

[3] Vuong QH. (2023). *Mindsponge Theory*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH.

